
ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY AND PERFORMANCE OF CIVIL SERVANTS IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract: The study evaluated the economic sustainability and performance of civil servants in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to; verify the relationship between cost savings and problem-solving ability; and examine the relationship between job creation and work output of civil servants in Enugu State. The area of the study was Enugu State. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 288 selected civil servants was used. The whole population was used to due small number. Two hundred and forty-eight (248) respondents returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed using Likert Scale and the hypotheses tested using Z – test. The findings indicated that there was significant positive relationship between cost savings and problem-solving quality, $Z = 10.160$, $P = .05$. There was significant positive relationship between job creation and work output of civil servants in Enugu State. $Z = 10.859$, $P = .05$. the study concluded that Economic sustainability is a key factor influencing the performance of civil servants in Enugu State. A stable and supportive economic environment enhances job satisfaction, promotes efficiency, and enables civil servants to perform their duties effectively. The study recommended among others that the government should implement cost-effective measures, such as optimizing resource allocation and reducing waste, to ensure financial sustainability while maintaining efficient public services.

Keywords: Cost savings, Economic sustainability, Job creation & Performance.

Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Economic sustainability has gained significant attention in both public and private sectors, particularly in developing economies like Nigeria, where managing resources efficiently is vital for long-term growth. It involves ensuring that economic practices support growth without causing long-term harm to social, environmental, or cultural aspects (Kahraman, 2023). The performance of civil servants is central to ensuring that economic sustainability is achieved, especially as Nigeria faces ongoing economic challenges, such as inflation, unemployment, and limited fiscal resources (Hassan and Lawal, 2023). Recent studies suggest that for the civil service to contribute to long-term economic sustainability, it must focus on effective resource

utilization and fostering an environment conducive to innovation and problem-solving (Olatunji, Akande, Taiwo and Emmanuel, 2022).

Performance in the public sector is often evaluated based on efficiency, productivity, and the capacity to deliver services. Several studies highlight the importance of problem-solving in improving public service delivery. According to Nwankwo (2022), effective problem-solving in the public sector not only enhances resource management but also fosters a culture of continuous improvement. Moreover, Pham, Do, Doan, Nguyen and Pham (2021) argue that when civil servants utilize cost-saving techniques, they contribute to the efficiency of government operations, leading to more sustainable economic practices. Job creation is another vital factor influencing the performance of civil servants, particularly in economies struggling with high unemployment rates like Nigeria. Research by Oguchi (2018) and Madiha Muhammad and Ambreen, (2023) shows that job creation not only enhances individual productivity but also contributes to a broader national economic agenda by reducing poverty and improving social welfare. In Enugu State, job creation within the public sector can lead to higher work output among civil servants, as employees tend to be more motivated and productive when they feel secure in their roles and see opportunities for advancement.

The link between job creation and work output, however, remains underexplored with regards to the civil servants in Enugu State. This study aims to examine how job creation initiatives can influence the work output of civil servants, contributing to both their personal performance and broader economic sustainability efforts (Oguchi, 2018; Madiha, Muhammad and Ambreen, 2023). By investigating the relationship between these variables, this research seeks to provide useful results for policy makers aiming to enhance civil service productivity and economic development in Nigeria. The results of the study are also going to be helpful for the government in their effort to maximize worker productivity. In light of this, the study seeks to evaluate the relationship between economic sustainability and performance of civil servants in Enugu State.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Economic sustainability and workforce performance are critical to the efficiency of any public sector, ensuring optimal resource utilization and service delivery. In an ideal scenario, civil servants operate in a well-structured system where cost-saving measures do not compromise productivity but instead enhance efficiency. Job creation within the public sector is strategically aligned with workforce demands, ensuring that employees are neither overburdened nor underutilized. When these factors are effectively managed, civil servants can maximize their problem-solving abilities, improve work output, and contribute meaningfully to economic growth and stability. This balance fosters a productive workforce, improves governance, and enhances the overall development of Enugu State.

However, in reality, the civil service in Enugu State faces challenges related to economic sustainability, particularly in cost savings and job creation. Inefficiencies in resource allocation often lead to financial wastage, limiting the government's ability to implement effective cost-saving strategies that enhance productivity. Without proper fiscal management, civil servants may lack the necessary resources and incentives to develop their problem-solving skills, reducing their efficiency. Similarly, inadequate job creation results in an overstretched workforce, where employees struggle with excessive workloads, leading to decreased morale and

lower work output. The inability to create and maintain an optimal workforce structure hampers the overall performance of civil servants, affecting service delivery in the state.

The consequences of these challenges are far-reaching, impacting governance, economic sustainability, and public service efficiency. Poor cost-saving mechanisms contribute to financial mismanagement, reducing funds available for critical government projects and employee development initiatives. A lack of job creation results in unemployment or underemployment, leading to lower motivation and productivity among civil servants. Ultimately, these issues can cause a decline in service quality, reduced public trust in government institutions, and slowed economic growth. If these problems persist, the effectiveness of the civil service in Enugu State will continue to deteriorate, affecting the overall development and well-being of its citizens.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to examine economic sustainability and performance of civil servants in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to;

- i. Verify the relationship between cost savings and problem-solving ability of civil servants in Enugu State.
- ii. Examine the relationship between job creation and work output of civil servants in Enugu State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

- i. What is the relationship between cost savings and problem-solving quality of civil servants in Enugu State?
- ii. What is the relationship between job creation and work output of civil servants in Enugu State?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study;

- i. There is no relationship between cost savings and problem-solving quality of civil servants in Enugu State.
- ii. There is no relationship between job creation and work output of civil servants in Enugu State

1.6 Significance of the Study

The significance of this study extends to multiple key stakeholders, including government policymakers, civil servants, economists, and the general public. For government policymakers, the study provides valuable insights into how cost-saving measures and job creation influence the economic sustainability and performance of civil servants in Enugu State, enabling them to formulate more effective public sector policies. Civil servants stand to benefit as the findings highlight the impact of problem-solving abilities and work output on job efficiency, potentially leading to better training opportunities and improved working conditions. Economists and researchers can utilize the study's findings to analyze broader economic sustainability trends within the public sector, contributing to academic discourse and future research. Lastly, the general public benefits indirectly, as enhanced performance in the civil service translates to better governance, improved service delivery, and overall economic growth, fostering a more sustainable and productive society.

1.7 Scope of the Study

This study focuses on the economic sustainability and performance of civil servants in Enugu State, examining the impact of cost savings on problem-solving ability and job creation on work output. It is limited to civil servants in government ministries, departments, and agencies (MDAs) within Enugu State. The study analyzes

recent economic trends and policies affecting the civil service, using quantitative and qualitative methods to gather data.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Economic Sustainability

Sustainability is an emerging and rapidly growing interdisciplinary field of research, closely related to the economic implications of environmental issues for different industries and firms, and the need of transition to a sustainable economy (Sauve, Bernard & Sloan, 2016) According to Doane and MacGillivray (2001), business sustainability is the business of staying in business. Economic sustainability involves managing resources to support long-term economic growth without compromising environmental health or social well-being. It requires balancing economic development with environmental conservation and social equity. Recent studies emphasize the integration of economic, social, and environmental dimensions to achieve sustainable development (Fiaramonti, 2020). Economic sustainability is thus understood to be economic development that cannot cause a loss of ecological or social sustainability. An increase in economic capital cannot be at the expense of a reduction in natural capital or social capital. Economic sustainability is interpreted as the allocation of resources over time (Markulev and Long, 2013). Hawken, Lovins and Lovins (2017) argue that economic sustainability involves practices that allow a system or business to produce economic value without diminishing natural and human resources over time. Sachs (2015) describes economic sustainability as "the management of resources to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

2.1.2 Components of Economic Sustainability

2.1.2.1 Cost Savings

As Chukwugbo (2005) opined, cost is the worth of a unit of product or service. It is the amount of money spent in procuring a thing or product commodity. The importance and necessity of cost to shareholders, investors, tax agencies, and creditors are not overawed in period reporting. Cost savings refer to the reduction of operational expenses without compromising the effectiveness or quality of services delivered. It involves identifying areas where expenditure can be minimized through more efficient resource allocation (Babatunde, Adeniyi and Adebayo, 2019). In the public sector, cost savings are achieved by reducing waste, enhancing productivity, and optimizing the use of available resources. This often requires strategic planning and improved administrative practices (Fujii, Yamaguchi and Okuda, 2020). Cost savings in government operations refer to efforts aimed at reducing unnecessary expenditures through better management of public funds, which can include policy reforms, staff training, and technology integration (Ibrahim & Gani, 2018).

2.1.2.2 Job Creation

Job creation plays a pivotal role in the economic revitalization of developing nations, as it serves as a fundamental driver of economic growth and poverty alleviation. According to Ayyagari, Demirgüç-Kunt and Maksimovic (2011), the adoption of policies that promote small and medium-sized investment projects is central to employment generation. These projects act as catalysts for new job opportunities, helping to reduce unemployment-related poverty and contribute to long-term economic expansion (Decker, Haltiwanga, Jarmin

and Miranda, 2014). However, generating net new jobs is a complex process that requires well-structured policies and strategic implementation (Haltiwanger, Jarming and Miranda, 2013; Ram, Aghahosseini and Breyer, 2020). The net job creation rate is determined by subtracting the number of old jobs lost from the number of new jobs created, providing a metric for economic progress through employment growth (Shane, 2009). This process ensures that economic stability is maintained by continuously replenishing skills and capabilities within the workforce (Wei, Patadia and Karmen, 2010).

2.1.3 Performance of Civil Servants

Performance is the accomplishment of a given task measured against preset known standards of accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed. For civil servants, this definition shows the necessity of setting clear expectations in terms of performance targets, such as timeliness, accuracy in administrative tasks, and the quality of public services delivered. Regular assessment of civil servants' performance can guide improvements and accountability in public administration. Aguinis (2019) defines performance as the record of outcomes produced on a specified job function or activity during a specified time period. Aguinis (2009) opined that performance is also influenced by "individual characteristics and environmental factors," indicating that a civil servant's job performance is shaped by both their personal abilities (skills, knowledge) and the work environment (resources, organizational support). The external factors, such as political stability or available technology, play a crucial role in public service performance.

2.1.4 Components of Performance

2.1.4.1 Problem Solving

Problem-solving involves identifying, analyzing, and resolving issues to achieve desired outcomes. It encompasses various stages, including problem identification, information gathering, generating potential solutions, evaluating alternatives, and implementing the chosen solution (Rhodes, Richland and Alcalá, 2024). This process is essential across diverse fields, from mathematics and engineering to everyday life situations. Effective problem-solving is crucial for addressing public sector challenges, such as improving service delivery, formulating policies, and managing resources efficiently. Recent research emphasizes the importance of metacognitive skills—thinking about one's thinking—in enhancing problem-solving abilities. A study by Güner and Erbay (2021) highlights that metacognitive strategies enable individuals to monitor and regulate their cognitive processes, leading to more effective problem-solving outcomes. Research by Jukes, Ahmed, Baker, Drapper, Howard and McCoy (2024) underscores that problem-solving is deeply intertwined with context, suggesting that recognizing the specific circumstances and cultural factors influencing a problem can lead to more effective solutions.

2.1.4.2 Work Output

Work output refers to the measurable results of an individual's or organization's efforts within a specific period, often linked to productivity, efficiency, or quality of work. Recent studies emphasize the importance of both quantity and quality in determining work output. For example, Becker and Huselid (2020) define work output as the effective contribution of an individual toward organizational goals, where both the number of tasks completed and the standard of completion are considered critical performance metrics. Work output among civil servants often requires measuring not just the volume of work, but also how well it aligns with the service

standards expected by the public. In addition to individual work output, organizations may also focus on the overall efficiency of work processes. Aguinis (2019) highlights that work output is directly impacted by how efficiently work processes are designed and how well employees are supported in their roles. For civil servants, improving work output is often tied to better resource management, improved organizational structures, and continuous training programs aimed at skill enhancement.

2.1.5 Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Linkages

The diagram above shows the conceptual linkages in the study. The concepts in the study's objectives are closely linked, with each variable influencing the others. The first objective examines how cost savings can be impacted by the problem-solving ability of civil servants, suggesting that skilled problem-solvers are likely to find efficient solutions, leading to more effective use of resources and thus, cost savings. The second objective explores how job creation affects work output, proposing that creating more jobs for civil servants can lead to higher productivity, as a larger workforce would likely enhance overall efficiency and service delivery. Both of these relationships highlight how improvements in one area—whether through problem-solving skills or job creation—can directly contribute to better economic sustainability and increased performance in the public sector.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The study reviewed two theories in relation to its objectives. Of the theories reviewed, the study is anchored on the Human Capital Theory because it emphasizes the importance of individuals' skills, knowledge, and abilities in enhancing organizational performance and contributing to economic sustainability. The theory suggests that enhancing civil servants' problem-solving abilities can lead to more efficient resource utilization, ultimately improving performance and cost savings.

i. Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory (Wenerfelt, 1984)

ii. Human Capital Theory (Becker, G.S. 1964)

2.2.1 Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory

The Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory, initially introduced by Wernerfelt (1984) and later expanded by Barney (1991), argues that organizations gain a sustainable competitive advantage by effectively managing and

utilizing their unique resources. The theory is based on the assumption that resources must possess certain qualities valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) to contribute to long-term success (Barney, 1991). According to the RBV perspective, an organization's internal resources, such as skilled human capital, strong leadership, and institutional knowledge, are critical drivers of superior performance and economic sustainability (Peteraf, 1993). This theory shifts the focus from external market conditions to internal capabilities, emphasizing that organizations, including government institutions, can enhance their performance by leveraging their workforce as a strategic asset.

In the context of this study, the RBV Theory is relevant in examining the relationship between job creation and the work output of civil servants in Enugu State. By creating more job opportunities within the civil service, the government can optimize human capital utilization, enhance productivity, and improve service delivery. A well-structured employment strategy ensures that the right individuals with specialized skills are placed in positions where they can contribute effectively, thereby increasing overall work efficiency and performance (Grant, 1996). Moreover, job creation leads to a motivated workforce, reducing the burden on existing employees and fostering a more efficient work environment. When civil servants are provided with stable employment and career growth opportunities, they are more likely to be committed to their roles, leading to better economic outcomes for the state. The RBV Theory, therefore, provides an essential framework for understanding how strategic resource management, particularly human resources, can contribute to the economic sustainability and performance of civil servants in Enugu State.

2.2.2 Human Capital Theory

The Human Capital Theory, developed by Becker (1964), emphasizes the significance of investing in individuals' knowledge, skills, and competencies to improve their productivity and economic contribution. The theory argues that education, training, and work experience are essential for enhancing an individual's ability to contribute effectively to an organization or economy. It assumes that individuals with better education and skill sets tend to be more innovative, efficient, and capable of solving complex problems, which in turn leads to higher economic growth and sustainability (Schultz, 1961). The theory highlights that human capital, just like physical capital, requires investment to yield optimal returns. Governments and organizations that prioritize human capital development are more likely to achieve long-term economic stability, as a skilled workforce is better equipped to handle economic challenges and drive organizational success.

The Human Capital Theory is highly relevant in explaining the relationship between cost savings and the problem-solving ability of civil servants in Enugu State. Cost-saving measures in the civil service often require strategic decision-making, financial prudence, and efficiency, all of which are enhanced by a workforce with strong analytical and problem-solving skills. Civil servants who have undergone continuous training and skill development are more likely to identify inefficiencies, propose innovative solutions, and implement policies that enhance economic sustainability. Additionally, a well-trained workforce can contribute to better governance, transparency, and accountability, further strengthening the economic framework of the state (Psacharopoulos & Patrinos, 2004). Thus, the Human Capital Theory provides a strong foundation for understanding how the development of civil servants' skills can lead to improved cost management and overall economic sustainability.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Cost Savings and Problem Solving

Ogbuagu and Obi (2020) examined the effect of cost reduction techniques on profitability of manufacturing firms. To achieve this objective, the study adopted survey design. Data were collected from the primary source. A total of 120 copies of questionnaire were administered out of which only 100 were retrieved. The returned copies of questionnaire were utilized in the data analysis of the study. Simple regression model was established

and the findings of the study indicate that there is a significant relationship between cost reduction techniques and organizational profitability. The study concludes that the application of cost reduction techniques has improved organizational profitability.

Pham, Do, Doan, Nguyen and Pham (2021) empirically explored the influence of sustainability practices on the financial performance of 116 listed Swedish companies in the year 2019. The research findings indicate a positive relationship between corporate sustainability and financial performance that is measured by earnings yield, return on asset, return on equity and return on capital employed. However, when it comes to a market-based financial measure, Tobin's Q, the result is inconclusive. Finally, to improve financial performance, firms are recommended to engaging in Dow Jones Sustainability Index, prepare their sustainability report in accordance with Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) Standards, improve their sustainable growth rate, as well as keep a high position in the corporate social responsibility ranking.

Hassan and Lawal (2021) explored the role of the civil service as a contributor to Nigeria's sustainable economic development. The methodology adopted was a documentary review and contextual analysis of past and current literature on the impact of civil service on sustainable economic development in Nigeria. The inefficiency and incompetency of the Nigerian civil service are evident due to the poor execution of the national budgets and public policies geared towards economic development. Furthermore, the unpredictability of the Nigerian political and economic sector and the high cost of doing business which is undermining investors' confidence is another important negative effect on Nigerian civil service performance in promotion of sustainable economic development.

Olatunji, Akande, Taiwo and Emmanuel (2022) examined the effect of sustainability disclosure on financial performance of selected listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The population of the study comprises all the 12 listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The study used secondary data obtained from annual report of only ten (10) oil and gas publicly traded firms on the Nigerian stock Exchange covering a period of 5 years ranging from 2016 -2020. The research design that was adopted in this study was ex-post research design. The panel regression estimation technique was employed to investigate to what extent financial performance is affected by sustainability disclosure of the selected firms. Findings of this study revealed that environmental sustainability disclosure has statistically significant positive effect (P-value of 0.0227) on financial performance at 5% level of significant). Furthermore, economic sustainability disclosure and social sustainability disclosure has statistically insignificant effect on financial performance of selected listed firms in Nigeria. The study concluded that environmental sustainability disclosure has impacted positively on financial performance of companies investigated.

Korolo and Korolo (2023) investigated the relationship between corporate sustainability reporting and the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to determine whether economic, social, and environmental sustainability reporting affects financial performance in Nigeria using return on assets (ROA) as a measure of corporate financial performance. The study's data were sourced from annual reports of sampled banks from 2013-2022. Using the panel least squares regression technique, the study found that economic and environmental sustainability reporting has a negative and positive insignificant effect on the performance respectively. However, social sustainability reporting was found to be negative and statistically significant.

2.3.2 Job Creation and Work Output

Oguchi (2018) examined the extent to which issues of poverty alleviation and inequality are being addressed through job creation. It is a qualitative study in which data was obtained from secondary sources such as books, journals, periodicals, magazines, internet, etc. Content analysis is employed in its methodology while neo-classical theory of a linear closed system was adopted as the theoretical framework. The paper is structured in

the order of introduction, problem statement, the literature (conceptual, theoretical framework, empirical) and the gap. The results of the analysis revealed that while efforts have been made to create jobs for the teeming population, such efforts have not come far enough in ameliorating the unemployment situation.

Olutola (2022) examined the effect of sustainability reporting (SR) on the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria from 2010 to 2020. A sample of 24 businesses from 8 industries was taken using an ex post facto research design. Panel regression analysis was used to analyze data taken from their annual report. The study discovered that whereas CRS has a negative, negligible impact on financial performance, DP, ERS, and R&D have a positive, significant relationship with financial performance. The study concluded that SR positively affects the financial performance of Nigerian-listed manufacturing enterprises based on its findings.

Madiha, Muhammad, and Ambreen (2023) investigated the relationship between economic growth and employment in Pakistan at the aggregate and sectoral levels. It uses different econometric models, such as the Cobb-Douglas production function, the employment demand model, and the ARDL model, to analyze the data and test the hypotheses. It finds that economic growth does not create enough jobs for the population and that there is a mismatch between the output and employment growth of different sectors. It shows that the service sector, which is the fastest-growing sector in Pakistan, has a contradictory and weak impact on employment and growth, and that it relies on more capital-intensive technology.

Ojimba, Okafor, Okeke and Mbah (2023) examined economic environment and organizational performance in pharmaceutical, firms in Anambra State. The area of this study is Anambra state which is a state in southeastern part of Nigeria. The population of the study was two thousand four hundred and ninety-five (2495). The sample size of 479 was gotten through Borg and Gall formular. The reliability of responses to the items of the instruments was analysed using cronbach coefficient alpha aided with the use of SPSS 23. The reliability coefficient shows that the questionnaire yield 0.75%, which indicates that the instrument is reliable. Meanwhile percentage table, correlation and regression analysis were used to analyze the collected data from the sample respondents. The study found that Interest rate has significant negative effect on organizational performance in pharmaceutical firms Anambra state. Inflation rate has negative and significant effect on organizational performance in pharmaceutical firms Anambra state. Exchange rate has a positive and significant effect on organizational performance in pharmaceutical firms Anambra state.

Weerasinghe, Weerasinghe, Perera, Tennakon, Rathnayake and Jayasinghe (2023) examined the impact of multi-dimensional corporate sustainability practices on organizational performance in the said sector. The study employed the partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) technique for analysing and testing the hypothesis of the study while using Smart PLS 4.0 software as the analysis tool. Relevant data were collected through a questionnaire from 300 apparel firms registered with the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI). The study results indicated that "economic vigour," "ethical practices," and "social equity" have a significant impact on organizational performance, while "corporate governance" and "environmental performance" have an insignificant impact. Unique discoveries from this study would be useful to prosper organizational performance and formulate novel sustainable future strategies not limited to the garment industry even during harsh economic conditions.

2.4 Summary and Gap in Empirical Review

Despite the numerous studies on economic sustainability and organizational performance, there remains a gap in knowledge regarding how these concepts specifically relate to civil servants, particularly in the context of Enugu State. While previous studies have explored the effects of cost reduction techniques on organizational profitability (Ogbuagu & Obi, 2020) and the role of sustainability practices in financial performance (Pham et al., 2021), few have examined the direct link between cost savings and the problem-solving abilities of civil

servants. Additionally, while research has delved into job creation's impact on organizational performance (Madiha et al., 2023; Oguchi, 2018), there is limited focus on how job creation influences the work output of civil servants in Nigeria, particularly in Enugu State. This study seeks to fill this gap by exploring how these variables specifically affect civil servants' performance and economic sustainability at the state level, contributing new insights into the public sector's role in promoting sustainable economic development.

3.0 Methodology

The area of the study was Enugu state, Nigeria. The study made use of 288 selected civil servants in Enugu metropolis, Enugu state of Nigeria. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. The whole population was used to due small number. Two hundred and forty-eight (248) respondents returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 8nnnnnn percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.86 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation. The hypotheses were tested using Z – test statistic tool.

4.0 Data Presentation

4.1. The relationship between cost savings and problem-solving ability of civil servants in Enugu State.

Table 4.1.1: Responses on the relationship between cost savings and problem-solving ability of civil servants in Enugu State.

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Civil servants who possess strong problem-solving skills can find creative ways to streamline processes and reduce wastage,	475	184	186	36	27	902	3.66	1.340	Agree
		95	46	62	18	27	248			
		38.3	18.5	25.0	7.3	10.9	100.0			
2	Effective problem-solvers often improve workflows and eliminate unnecessary steps in processes	740	184	48	26	25	1023	4.12	1.330	Agree
		148	46	16	13	25	248			
		59.7	18.5	6.5	5.2	10.1	100.0			
3	Problem-solving skills enable civil servants to interpret and act on data, creating cost-effective solutions	580	184	144	12	32	952	3.84	1.379	Agree
		116	46	48	6	32	248			
		46.8	18.5	19.4	2.4	12.9	100.0			
4	Civil servants who are trained in problem-solving techniques can better identify areas for cost reduction	625	412	21	28	7	1093	4.15	1.183	Agree
		129	74	16	11	18	248			
		52.0	29.8	6.5	4.4	7.3	100.0			
5	Saving costs may allow civil servants to think long-term about solving systemic issues, rather than focusing only on short-term financial constraints	800	228	15	12	20	1075	4.33	1.175	Agree
		160	57	5	6	20	248			
		64.5	23.0	2.0	2.4	8.1	100.0			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								4.020	1.2814	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1.1, 141 respondents out of 248 representing 56.8 percent agreed that Civil servants who possess strong problem-solving skills can find creative ways to streamline processes and reduce wastage with the mean score of 3.66 and standard deviation of 1.340. 194 respondents representing 78.2 percent agreed that Effective problem-solvers often improve workflows and eliminate unnecessary steps in processes with a mean score of

4.12 and standard deviation of 1.330. 216 respondents representing 65.3 Percent agreed that Problem-solving skills enable civil servants to interpret and act on data, creating cost-effective solutions with mean score of 3.84 and standard deviation of 1.379. 203 respondents representing 81.8 percent agreed that Civil servants who are trained in problem-solving techniques can better identify areas for cost reduction with mean score of 4.15 and standard deviation of 1.183. 217 respondents representing 87.5 percent agreed that saving costs may allow civil servants to think long-term about solving systemic issues, rather than focusing only on short-term financial constraints, with a mean score of 4.33 and standard deviation 1.175.

4.2. The relationship between job creation and work output of civil servants in Enugu State.

Table 4.2.1: Responses on the relationship between job creation and work output of civil servants in Enugu State.

		5	4	3	2	1	∑FX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Job creation in the public sector lead to a more balanced distribution of work. By hiring more civil servants	555 111 44.8	340 85 34.3	12 4 1.6	54 27 10.9	21 21 8.5	982 248 100.0	3.96	1.291	Agree
2	Efficient civil servants who are better supported in their roles contribute more effectively to societal development.	580 116 46.8	372 93 37.5	15 5 2.0	20 10 4.0	24 24 9.7	1011 248 100.0	4.08	1.233	Agree
3	Reforms that focus on better management practices and digitalization, make civil servants more productive.	705 141 56.9	328 82 33.1	12 4 1.6	20 10 4.0	11 11 4.4	1076 256 100.0	4.46	.903	Agree
4	When job creation leads to more stable employment opportunities, it boosts morale and job satisfaction.	630 126 50.8	380 95 38.3	9 3 1.2	12 6 2.4	18 18 7.3	1049 248 100.0	4.23	1.106	Agree
5	Civil servants who feel secure in their positions may be more motivated to perform at their best, improving overall productivity	420 84 33.9	436 109 44.0	9 3 1.2	58 29 11.7	23 23 9.3	946 248 100.0	3.81	1.275	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								4.108	1.1616	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.1, 196 respondents out of 248 representing 79.1 percent agreed that Job creation in the public sector led to a more balanced distribution of work by hiring more civil servants with the mean score of 3.96 and standard deviation of 1.291. 209 respondents representing 84.3 percent agreed that efficient civil servants who are better supported in their roles contribute more effectively to societal development with a mean score of 4.08 and standard deviation of 1.233. 223 respondents representing 90.0 Percent agreed that Reforms that focus on better management practices and digitalization make civil servants more productive with mean score of 4.46 and standard deviation of .903. 221 respondents representing 89.1 percent agreed that When job creation leads to more stable employment opportunities, it boosts morale and job satisfaction with mean score of 4.23 and standard deviation of 1.106. 193 respondents representing 77.9 percent agreed that Civil servants who feel secure in their positions may be more motivated to perform at their best, improving overall productivity, with a mean score of 3.81 and standard deviation 1.275.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

4.3.1 There is no relationship between cost savings and problem-solving quality of civil servants in Enugu State.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Civil servants who possess strong problem-solving skills can find creative ways to streamline processes and reduce wastage,	Effective problem-solvers often improve workflows and eliminate unnecessary steps in processes	Problem-solving skills enable civil servants to interpret and act on data, creating cost-effective solutions	Civil servants who are trained in problem-solving techniques can better identify areas for cost reduction	Saving costs may allow civil servants to think long-term about solving systemic issues, rather than focusing only on short-term financial constraints
N		248	248	248	248	248
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute Positive	.383	.597	.468	.569	.645
	Negative	-.109	-.101	-.129	-.073	-.081
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		6.033	9.398	7.366	8.954	10.160
	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – values ranging from $6.033 < 10.160$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms that the assertion of the most of the respondents **there was significant positive relationship between cost savings and problem-solving quality of civil servants in Enugu State.**

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- values ranging from $6.033 < 10.160$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 97% level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that there was significant positive relationship between cost savings and problem-solving quality of civil servants in Enugu State.

4.3.2 There is no relationship between job creation and work output of civil servants in Enugu State

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Job creation in the public sector lead to a more balanced distribution of work. By hiring more civil servants	Efficient civil servants who are better supported in their roles contribute more effectively to societal development.	Reforms that focus on better management practices and digitalization, make civil servants more productive.	When job creation leads to more stable employment opportunities, it boost morale and job satisfaction.	Civil servants who feel secure in their positions may be more motivated to perform at their best, improving overall productivity
N		248	248	248	248	248
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute Positive	.540	.593	.690	.641	.528
	Negative	-.085	-.097	-.044	-.073	-.093
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		8.509	9.335	10.859	10.097	8.319
	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – values ranging from $8.319 < 10.859$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms that the assertion of the most of the respondents **there was significant positive relationship between job creation and work output of civil servants in Enugu State.**

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- values ranging from $8.319 < 10.859$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 97% level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that **there was significant positive relationship between job creation and work output of civil servants in Enugu State**

4.4 Discussion of findings

4.4.1 There was significant positive relationship between cost savings and problem-solving quality of civil servants in Enugu State.

From the result of the hypotheses one, the calculated Z- values ranging from $6.033 < 10.160$ against the critical Z- value of .000 which implies that there was significant positive relationship between cost savings and problem-solving quality of civil servants in Enugu State. In the support of result in the literature review, Ogbuagu and Obi (2020) examined the effect of cost reduction techniques on profitability of manufacturing firms. Simple regression model was established and the findings of the study indicate that there is a significant relationship between cost reduction techniques and organizational profitability. Hassan and Lawal (2021) explored the role of the civil service as a contributor to Nigeria's sustainable economic development. The methodology adopted was a documentary review and contextual analysis of past and current literature on the impact of civil service on sustainable economic development in Nigeria. The inefficiency and incompetency of the Nigerian civil service are evident due to the poor execution of the national budgets and public policies geared towards economic development

4.4.2 There was significant positive relationship between job creation and work output of civil servants in Enugu State

From the result of the hypotheses two, comparing the calculated Z- values ranging from $8.319 < 10.859$ against the critical Z- value of .000 which implies that there was significant positive relationship between job creation and work output of civil servants in Enugu State. In the support of result in the literature review, Oguchi (2018) examined the extent to which issues of poverty alleviation and inequality are being addressed through job creation. It is a qualitative study in which data was obtained from secondary sources such as books, journals, periodicals, magazines, internet, etc. Content analysis is employed in its methodology while neo-classical theory of a linear closed system was adopted as the theoretical framework. The results of the analysis revealed that while efforts have been made to create jobs for the teeming population, such efforts have not come far enough in ameliorating the unemployment situation. Ojimba, Okafor, Okeke and Mbah (2023) examined economic environment and organizational performance in pharmaceutical, firms in Anambra State. Meanwhile

percentage table, correlation and regression analysis were used to analyze the collected data from the sample respondents. The study found that Interest rate has significant negative effect on organizational performance in pharmaceutical firms Anambra state. Inflation rate has negative and significant effect on organizational performance in pharmaceutical firms Anambra state. Exchange rate has a positive and significant effect on organizational performance in pharmaceutical firms Anambra state (Weerasinghe et al., 2023).

5.0 Summary of findings, conclusion, recommendations and contribution to knowledge

5.1 Summary of findings

- i. There was significant positive relationship between cost savings and problem-solving quality of civil servants in Enugu State. $Z = 10.160$
- ii. There was significant positive relationship between job creation and work output of civil servants in Enugu State. $Z = 10.859$

5.2 Conclusion

Economic sustainability is a key factor influencing the performance of civil servants in Enugu State. A stable and supportive economic environment enhances job satisfaction, promotes efficiency, and enables civil servants to perform their duties effectively. As such, ensuring long-term economic stability is essential for improving the overall productivity of the public sector and contributing to the growth of the state.

5.3 Recommendations

- i. The government should implement cost-effective measures, such as optimizing resource allocation and reducing waste, to ensure financial sustainability while maintaining efficient public services.
- ii. To further enhance economic growth, the government should focus on creating more job opportunities within the civil service by promoting skill development programs and expanding public sector projects.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

Despite the numerous studies on economic sustainability and organizational performance, there remains a gap in knowledge regarding how these concepts specifically relate to civil servants, particularly in the context of Enugu State. While previous studies have explored the effects of cost reduction techniques on organizational profitability (Ogbuagu & Obi, 2020) and the role of sustainability practices in financial performance (Pham et al., 2021), few have examined the direct link between cost savings and the problem-solving abilities of civil servants. Additionally, while research has delved into job creation's impact on organizational performance (Madiha et al., 2023; Oguchi, 2018), there is limited focus on how job creation influences the work output of civil servants in Nigeria, particularly in Enugu State. This study seeks to fill this gap by exploring how these variables specifically affect civil servants' performance and economic sustainability at the state level, contributing new insights into the public sector's role in promoting sustainable economic development.

Conceptual framework adds to the contribution to knowledge.

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